

SOME COMMENTS REGARDING THE EARLY PREVENTION OF VIOLENCE OFFENSES IN VIRTUAL SPACE.

Shukurov Otabek Bakhodirovich

Responsible official of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15075422>

Abstract: This article addresses the issue of early prevention of fraudulent offenses in cyberspace. With the advancement of modern digital technologies, instances of cybercrime, identity theft, and illegal activities on online platforms are on the rise. The article examines measures to prevent these problems, such as improving legislation, enhancing the population's digital literacy, utilizing technologies, and strengthening international cooperation. It also analyzes the practices and prospects for ensuring cybersecurity in Uzbekistan. The aim of the research is to identify effective methods of combating fraud in cyberspace and to provide recommendations for their implementation.

Keywords: Cyberspace, cybercrime, offense, digital literacy, cybersecurity, legislation, technology, international cooperation.

The rapid development of digital technologies and the Internet is profoundly impacting all spheres of human life, including the economy, social relations, and information exchange. However, alongside this process, fraudulent activities in the virtual space are increasing daily, becoming a factor that poses serious risks. Phishing emails, theft of personal data, fake messages on online platforms, and other cybercrime methods are not only causing material damage to the population but also undermining their trust in digital security. To prevent this problem early on, it is crucial to implement comprehensive measures such as strengthening the legislative framework, enhancing the population's digital literacy, utilizing modern technologies, and bolstering international cooperation. This article examines effective methods of combating fraud in the virtual space, existing experiences in Uzbekistan, and future prospects in this area.

In recent years, a significant increase in the number of cybercrimes related to malicious online activities has been observed. For example, in 2024, more than 12 million attempted cyberattacks were recorded, while in 2023 this figure was 11 million[1]. Notably, cases of fraud have increased by 34%, and nearly 35% of all complaints are related to payment card fraud. It is emphasized that one of the main reasons for the increase in fraud cases is the growing number of bank card users. At the beginning of the year, their number was less than 40 million, and now it is reported to have exceeded 55 million[2].

Identifying the perpetrators of crimes committed in this area and recovering funds stolen through cyber fraud is a very difficult process, and the situation is further complicated by the fact that fraud can be committed by anyone from any part of the world. In such a situation, organizing early prevention of fraud in the virtual space is not only the responsibility of law enforcement agencies but also the duty of various civil society institutions, banks, state and non-state organizations engaged in electronic money circulation, the general public, and even ordinary citizens. Indeed, the aforementioned organizations and

agencies need to establish collaborative efforts to identify and eliminate any factors contributing to the commission of fraud in virtual space.

Based on this, interested agencies, in identifying cases of fraud in the virtual space and eliminating its causes and conditions, must: strictly adhere to the law; maintain a high level of legal culture; consider public opinion on fraud prevention; consistently rely on mutual assistance; promptly address applications, complaints, and reports from legal entities and individuals regarding fraud; and take appropriate legal measures.

At present, while analyzing the shortcomings in combating fraudulent crimes in virtual space in practice, the following factors that positively influence the effectiveness of fighting against this type of crime should be taken into account:

systematizing the regulatory documents that define the strategy for combating fraud crimes in virtual space into a unified standard system and revising them to adapt to the needs of personnel fighting against such crimes;

establishing widespread use of public assistance in combating fraudulent crimes in virtual space, and for this purpose, through mass media, instilling in the public consciousness the aspects of fraudulent crimes in virtual space that cause both material and moral harm to the whole society, and even physical harm to our citizens, while intensifying extensive propaganda and awareness-raising efforts;

expanding the scope and improving the quality of the fight against fraud in virtual space, taking into account the covert nature of these crimes;

establishing reliable, accurate, and effective cooperation between all services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, State Security Service, Customs system, Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the Prosecutor General's Office and other law enforcement agencies, as well as organizations engaged in banking, finance, and electronic money circulation within the territory of the republic.

The implementation of the following proposals will serve to achieve high efficiency in preventing and proactively addressing fraud crimes in the virtual space:

ensuring access for all interested parties by integrating existing software systems of law enforcement and other agencies into a single platform, as well as allocating the latest generation servers to district and city internal affairs bodies for the flawless operation of the newly created software system;

reviewing staffing issues and recruiting specialist personnel in response to the increasing cases of criminal misappropriation of funds from citizens' bank cards using information technologies and rising reports of cyber fraud;

recommending plastic card holders to be more vigilant when purchasing services through websites and online stores, to carefully review the terms of purchase and the website's public offer, to handle cards with caution, and to prevent unauthorized access to card information;

to prevent fraudulent crimes in virtual space, implementing full serving of sentences until the damages are fully paid in correctional institutions, as well as until these damages are compensated through work;

ensuring reliable cybersecurity in information systems of enterprises, educational institutions, and families, and improving the culture of Internet use among Internet users is of great importance for the prevention of fraudulent crimes in virtual space.

We believe that considering the aforementioned factors will have a positive impact on increasing the effectiveness of combating fraud crimes in the virtual space. The effective organization of this social partnership serves not only to prevent fraud in the virtual space at an early stage but also to increase the population's knowledge and legal awareness related to electronic money circulation, as well as to establish a healthy lifestyle among them.

References:

1. Official information of the Cybersecurity Center 2. In Uzbekistan, over 12 million cyberattacks were carried out in a year // URL: <https://kun.uz/ru/news/2025/02/03/v-uzbekistane-za-god-soversheno-svyshe-12-mln-kiberatak>
2. In Uzbekistan, over 12 million cyberattacks were carried out per year // URL: <https://kun.uz/ru/news/2025/02/03/v-uzbekistane-za-god-soversheno-svyshe-12-mln-kiberatak>

